

Sexual Exploitation of Children Online with Regard to the Jordanian Cybercrime act no. 27 of 2015

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Abstract

This research aims to address the crime of sexual exploitation of children online in the Jordanian the Cybercrime Act No. 27 of 2015, as the crimes related to the sexual exploitation of children are among the most dangerous crimes that affect society in general and childhood in particular.

This research has clarified the legal provisions for this crime, through an analysis of the provision of Article 9 of the Cybercrime Act No. 27 of 2015, where I concluded that this crime consists of two elements: Actus Reus & Mens Rea.

1. Introduction

The development occurring in the field of information and communication technology, especially the internet, has a great impact on the growth and worsening of the phenomenon of sexual exploitation of children and the development of its methods. Despite the positive role of the Internet and its use in various areas of life, this development has had another negative side that is very dangerous for children's lives, such as its use by bad persons who have sexual inclinations towards children. There are also criminal organizations that exploit children in pornography.

The exploitation of children online is considered one of the most dangerous criminal phenomena that constitute an indecent assault to the child. It also constituted an economic exploitation of the child's honor, weakness, and deficiencies in his mental and physical capabilities, as well as an exploitation thereof in acts harmful to his physical, mental, moral, and social development (Ali, 2017).

Therefore, law has to protect children from the risk of this exploitation. This is, in fact, one of the core competencies of law, according to the provision of the fifth paragraph of Article 6 of the Jordanian Constitution, which states, "Law shall protect maternity, childhood and old age. It shall also look after young people and people with disabilities and protect all from abuse and exploitation (Constitution, 2011).

The past decade has witnessed a rapid development in the use of electronic communications based on the exchange of information online, which has increased the risk of sexual exploitation of children for several reasons, the most important of which are:

Children may have access to major pornographic sites regulating child prostitution online.

Producers of child prostitution have found the Internet as a suitable place to sell their products of materials and films for this prostitution.

People who are attracted to children catch their victims through chatting, since one can be disguised online to become another person (Ash-Shawabkah, 2011).

As the subject of this research is related to crimes against public morals and ethics represented in pornographic acts, as addressed by the Jordanian Information Technology Crime Act through the provision of Article 9 of 27 of 2015, the focus will be on this crime rather than any other crimes.

Research importance

It is well established that this issue is of great importance, as this crime is one of the main social problems that affect society in general and children in particular. Studying such an issue requires the necessity of taking into account the specificity of its nature, as well as the specificity related to the regulations of law in terms of criminalization and punishment.

Research problem

This research was devoted to explaining the legal provisions related to the crime of sexual exploitation of children online in the Jordanian the Cybercrime Act No. 27 of 2015.

Whereas this crime is prescribed by the penal legislator, however it was not discussed as an extensive scientific discussion, so this research comes as an attempt to bridge the deficiency in this regard.

Research questions

The research attempts to answer the following questions:

1. What is the crime of sexual exploitation of children online? What about its elements?
2. How sufficient is the penalty in the Jordanian Cybercrime Act to prevent this crime?

Research Methodology

The researcher will follow the descriptive analytical method by explaining the provisions of the crime of sexual exploitation of children in accordance with the Cybercrime Act and its analysis. The forms of child sexual exploitation will be known online, as well as the family and international efforts to protect children from exploitation online.

WHAT IS CYBER PORNOGRAPHY

Explaining what cybercrime is one of the biggest dilemmas encountering legislators and jurists and law interpreters, since setting a comprehensive concept, as a definition agreed between the legislation of states and jurists, is a legislative challenge encountering internet legislation, as well as encountering the legislation of the virtual world as a whole. Perhaps the main reason for this is the diversity of cultures, ideologies and the environment. The legal systems of countries may be attributed, on the other hand, to the diversity of the private nature of electronic business and transactions, as well as to their crimes.

A cybercrime is defined as unlawful behavior by electronic devices that result in either material or moral damage to the victim and the criminal's obtaining material and moral benefits, or both. This is done with the aim of piracy in order to steal or destroy information. It is also known by other names such as high-tech crime (Ali, P. 56), computer crime and methods to confront it (Police Magazine, 2009), and criminal investigation into cybercrimes.

Cyber pornography was generally defined as any act or omission (including the responsibility of Internet service providers to report such crimes) that is represented by sending or publishing a pornographic business or by preparing, preserving, processing, displaying, printing, publishing or promoting pornographic activities or actions, or that which are related to prostitution and pornography (Musa, 2005).

Child pornography was defined as photographing any child, by any means, engaging in real practice or simulation of explicit sexual activities, or photographing a child's sexual organs mainly to satisfy sexual desire (Child Pornography, 2000).

ELEMENTS OF THE CRIME OF SEXUAL EXPLOITATION

Referring to the provision of Article (9) of the Cybercrime Act, we find that it includes three crimes, and each crime had its own penalty.

The crime of paragraph (a) of Article (9)

The crime of paragraph (a) of Article (9) criminalizes the exchange or transmission of material that includes pornographic activities or that which are related to sexual exploitation against those who have not reached the age of eighteen years, using information or any information network, in order to prevent the spread of such material and its circulation between people. It turns out that this crime is based on two elements: Actus Reus & Mens Rea.

Actus Reus

The behavior is to send or publish. The sending behavior is for specific people, whereas publishing is for unspecified people.

The provision also stipulates that the means used for transmission or publication shall be through an information system or information network, and if the publication is by traditional means, the provisions of this article do not apply thereto.

The issue of transmission or publishing pornographic material (whether audible, readable or visible) includes pornographic activities or that which are related to sexual exploitation against those who have not reached the age of eighteen.

In addition, the legislator did not stipulate that the material sent or published shall be real, but it could also be false, as this paragraph applies to whoever publishes pictures of children in different sexual positions regardless of being unreal.

Mens Rea

This crime is intentional. In order for this crime to be achieved, the legislator has requested the general criminal intent (knowledge and will), that is, the perpetrator is aware that he is carrying out a criminal activity or, in other words, he is aware that he knows that he is sending or publishing material through the information system or information network that includes pornographic activities or that which are related to sexual exploitation against those who have not reached the age of eighteen (Abu Issa, 2019). His will shall be directed to these acts. This is achieved with the knowledge of the perpetrator that he is sending or publishing material

through the information system or information network that includes pornographic activities or that which are related to sexual exploitation against those who have not reached the age of eighteen. Therefore, the perpetrator's will shall be directed to the achievement of sending or publishing.

Penalty

The perpetrator of this crime shall be punished with detention for a period of no less than three months and a fine no less than (300) three hundred dinars and not more than (5000) five thousand dinars.

The crime of Paragraph (b) of Article (9)

There has come in the explanatory note that this paragraph criminalizes anyone who intentionally used an information system or information network to influence, through pornographic activities and acts, a person who has not reached the age of eighteen or who is psychologically or mentally disabled.

It also criminalizes anyone who intentionally used information systems or the information network to direct or incite those who have not attained the age of eighteen years or who are mentally or mentally handicapped to commit a crime.

In addition, the acts set forth in Paragraph (b) intentionally directed at those under the age of eighteen, or those who are mentally handicapped, are criminalized, even if the material concerns events such as being pornographic acts involving adults (Crime Act, p. 12). Such a crime consists of two elements: Actus Reus & Mens Rea:

Actus Reus

Using an information system or information network to create, prepare, save, process, display, and print, publish, or promote pornographic activities or acts. It is noted that this crime punishes every person who commits one of these behaviors (Abu Issa, p. 132).

Mens Rea

This crime is intentional, and therefore it shall have the general criminal intent, along with the elements of knowledge and will, that is, the perpetrator knows that he engages in a criminal activity, and his will shall be directed to achieving the result.

It is also necessary for this crime to have a special intent. Hence, the purpose of the perpetrator is to influence those who are not yet eighteen years old or those who are mentally handicapped (Hosni p.132), or to direct or incite such minors to commit a crime. It is noted that the legislator did not stipulate a specific type of crime, as the term is absolute, so incitement to commit a sexual crime or incitement to commit any other crime are the same.

Penalty

The perpetrator of this crime shall be punished with imprisonment for a period of no less than two years and a fine no less than (1000) thousand dinars and not exceeding (5000) five thousand dinars.

The crime stipulated in clause (c) of Article (9)

Clause (c) discusses a more serious crime, which is the exploitation of a person who has not completed eighteen years of age or who is Intellectual or Psychological/Psychiatric Disability in prostitution or pornography, for instance, a person sending or announcing an offer to engage in a prostitution activity with children (Crime Act, p. 12), and this crime consists of two elements: Actus Reus & Mens Rea:

Actus Reus

Is the behavior of exploitation, which is benefitting by or making use of someone, and the text stipulated that the exploitation shall be limited to prostitution or pornography business only.

The exploited of this crime is any person who is not yet 18 years old, or any person who suffers from Intellectual or Psychological/Psychiatric Disability. The legislator also stipulated that the exploitation shall be by using an information system or the information network. Whoever exploits children by prostitution through customary means shall not apply this wording upon It, but the natural wording mentioned in the Penal Act apply to It.

Mens Rea

Mens Rea in this crime with the general criminal intent as the premeditated exploitation of the perpetrator, even if this conclusion was not actually proofed (Abu Issa, p. 132).

Penalty

The perpetrator of this crime shall be punished by interim penal servitude and with a fine of no less than (5000) five thousand dinars and not exceeding (15,000) fifteen thousand dinars.

Finally, there is a question arises in these crimes: Is the perpetrator required to know the child's age, meaning can the perpetrator submit Legal defenses that he was not aware that the exploited person is under eighteen?

It is legally established to rule in accordance with the assumption that the perpetrator knows the age of the victim in sexual crimes, unless It proves that Its ignorance of the age of the victim is due to force majeure or exceptional circumstances, and we see the validity of this rule to crimes of children sexual exploitation.

CATEGORIES OF CHILD SEXUAL EXPLOITATION VIA INTERNET

Experts have identified at least three areas of global threats that could expose children to further sexual abuse and exploitation (ECPAT International, 2016), which includes:

Alluring children via internet for sexual purposes (CEOP/NCA, 2013)

It is noticeable that the crime of alluring children via internet for sexual purposes has increased significantly.

Sexual Extortion

Also called "sextortion", is the extortion of a person (for his / her personal pictorial material for that person) to sexually extort It or exploit him for other benefits under the threat of sharing or publishing such material without the consent of the photographed person (such as publishing/posting photographs on social media or sending them to family members).

Making a Living via the Internet

Consequently, child sexual abuse can be considered online as a quick and easy source of income, and through live broadcasts it can generate revenues of up to \$ 1,000 per night (Lori 2012), Sometimes such crime is motivated, in part, by poverty.

FAMILY AND INTERNATIONAL EFFORTS TO PROTECT CHILDREN FROM EXPLOITATION VIA THE INTERNET

There are several family efforts to protect children from exploitation via the Internet, which are addressed below:

Technical measures

1. Using parental control software to delete any inappropriate content and monitor sites surfed by children and find out what they are doing by downloading the latest versions of the programs (Al-Sabea newspaper, 2014).
2. Demanding the company that delivers the internet service to automatically block porn sites (Al-Awsat newspaper, 2001).
3. There is an option provided by Microsoft on the Windows operating system, which enables parent to control the sites that the child has access to (Al-Sabea newspaper, 2014).
4. Secure browser, as Google provides the Google SafeSearch for parents to control the sites that children are allowed to access (Al-Sabea newspaper, 2014).

Educational measures

1. Setting rules for surfing the Internet with engaging children, thus through conversations with children to organize the time of surfing the Internet and the types of the sites that they access (Abdel Aal, 2014).
2. Warning children not to surfing dangerous or abnormal sites and not to give any personal information, pictures or address to them and not to give the password to anyone to their private pages or mail and to know the identity of the people who are with their children in the chat rooms and to urge the children to inform their parents of any mistake they committed (www.crdp.org/ar/details).
3. Instructing children to surf the Internet according to rules and ethics of public morals, and urging them not to post embarrassing content or images to others, without the knowledge of their parents, not to join suspicious groups, and not to promote ideas and issues that are contrary to morals and ethics, such as racism, violence, terrorism, or Sites promoting drug or suicide (www.crdp.org/ar/details).
4. International efforts made to protect children from exploitation in pornography via the internet, and among the most important international treaties that confronted this matter is the following:
 - The Optional Protocol on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography for the year 2000 (Child Pornography, 2000), which stated in its preamble: (The State parties... concerned about the increasing availability of pornography on the Internet and other emerging technologies, which the International Conference: Combating child pornography on the internet referenced (Vienna, 1999) (International Conference, 1999). In particular since the conference has ended on a note where it called for the criminalization of the production, distribution, export, broadcast, import of child pornography, intentional possession and promotion of it, and stressing the importance of closer cooperation and partnership between governments and the industry represented in the Internet.
 - Convention on the Rights of the Child (Rights of the Child): (Article 19) of the agreement obliged the State parties to protect children from all forms of violence, physical abuse, or the abuse of exploitation, which includes sexual abuse, and exploitation of children in prostitution and pornography.
 - Council of Europe Convention on the Protection of Children against Sexual Exploitation and Sexual Abuse of the year 2007 (Sexual Abuse), which stated in its preamble: (The State

parties of Europe and the other State parties signed to the current agreement... consider children sexual exploitation, especially the exploitation of children in prostitution and pornography and in all forms of sexual abuse including these actions committed abroad, are acts that harmful to the physical and psychosocial health of children...)

- In 2009, The General Assembly for the International Criminal Police Organization-INTERPOL has adopted the Act no. (AG-2009-RES-05) which is concerned with the sexual exploitation of children via the internet by using all of the available technical solutions.
- Arab Convention on Combating Technology Offences (Arab Convention) where the States parties has called for the criminalization of pornography on the internet in general, and child pornography is considered an aggravating circumstance, as article 12 of the Convention states the following: Pornography crimes:
 - a. Produce, display, distribute, provide, publish, buy, sell or import pornographic or obscene material via IT.
 - b. The penalty is increased for crimes relating to child and minors pornography.
 - c. The increasing of the plenty mentioned in paragraph 2 of this article includes possession of pornographic material for children and minors, or indecent material of children and minors, on IT or the storage medium for those technologies.

CONCLUSION

One of the most prominent obstacles facing cybercrime legislation in general - and what relates to cyber pornography in particular - in the Arab world, including Jordan - is the weak legislations related to the technical or practical aspect.

Cybercrime is one of the most serious threats to our society, across all spectrums. This study was conducted to display and clarify the concept of these crimes and the technical legal aspects associated with them, as the text of Article (9) was devoid of any definition indicating what is electronic porn crimes, which necessitated the necessity of resorting to a situation or trying to develop a definition that shows what this type of crime is.

This study reached a number of findings and recommendations, namely:

Results

1. Cyber pornography in terms of pillars is associated with traditional crimes, as the perpetrator must have the intention, purpose, and criminal motive, which is intended for the purpose of the act, whether or not the result was achieved, in a manner consistent with the nature of the digital or electronic environment based on science and will - Mens Rea- In addition to the public act - Actus Reus- in order to criminalize their action and then punish them.
2. The definition of cyber pornography has not been included in the IT Crime Law.
3. The legislator did not mention in Article (9 / A, B, C) any punishment for Internet service providers for any act related to sexual abuse, especially if he contacted the sexual exploitation of children.

The researcher has reached recommendations that are extremely important, as they are related to the nature of this type of crime and its implications for society in general and children in particular.

Recommendations

1. The necessity of stipulating a definition that clarifies the nature and nature of pornography cybercrimes, a path taken by most of the relevant national and international legislations in this field.
2. The legislator has a responsibility to unify the punishment with Article (9), Paragraph (a) and Paragraph (b), to become like the penalty for the crime of Paragraph (C), as this issue is a matter of priority, and at the responsibility of the legislator.
3. The legislator provides in Article (9 / A, B, and C) a penalty for Internet service providers for any act related to sexual abuse, especially if it is related to sexual exploitation of children.

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REFERENCES

Arabic

- Abu Issa, H. (2019). *IT Crimes, (Second Edition)*. Dar Wael Publishing.
- Al Janabihi, M. (2006). *Cybercrimes and the means to combat it, (First Edition)*. Dar Al Fikr Al Jamieiu.
- Al-Shawabkah, M.A. (2011). *Cybercrimes, (Second edition)*. Dar El Thaqafa, Amman.
- Hosni, M.N. (1974). *Irregular Criminals, (Second edition)*. Dar Al Nahda Al Arabia, Cairo.
- Musa, M.M. (2005). *Criminal techniques in digital technology - what it is and how to combat it (First Edition)*, Egypt, Dar al-Kutub Al Qanunia.

Kharashi, A.A (2015). Sexual exploitation of children crimes on the Internet and ways to combat them in criminal legislation and Islamic criminal jurisprudence, Dar aljameah aljadedah.

Master Theses

Sagheer, Y. (2013), *Crimes committed online*. Unpublished Master dissertation, Mouloud Ma'mari University.

Internet Source

ECPAT International (2016), "Briefing Paper: Emerging Global Threats Related to the Sexual Exploitation of Children Online", Bangkok: ECPAT International, from http://www.ecpat.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/Briefing-Paper_Emerging-global-threats-related-to-theseexual-exploitation-of-children-online.pdf, and ECPAT International OCSE Manifestation Factsheets (included in the Annexes section of this guide).

CEOP/NCA (2013), "Threat Assessment of Sexual Exploitation and Abuse", quoted in INTERPOL: "size of the problem" (8 July 2015), unpublished.

Handrahan, Lori (2012), "The Justice Department's Child Porn Problem", accessed March 2016, from <http://frontpagemag.com/2012/lori-handrahan/the-justice-departments-child-porn-problem/>.

Newspapers

Al-Youm Al-Sabea newspaper Article (Different Ways to Protect Your Children from Pornography Sites) published on Tuesday 14 / November / 2014

(Al-Sharq Al-Awsat newspaper, article (New ways to protect children from the dangers of the Internet and adults from misuse) published 2001

Protecting children and adolescents from the dangers of the Internet/ Dr. Abdel Nasser Abdel Aal, published on 3/8/2014, Oman National Computer Emergency Readiness Team)

Laws and Treaties

The Jordanian Constitution of 2011.

Jordanian Cybercrimes Act no. 27 for the year 2015.

The Optional Protocol on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography for the year 2000.

International Conference: Combating child pornography on the internet referenced (Vienna, 1999).

Convention on the Rights of the Child, Article 19 of the Convention.

Council of Europe Convention on the Protection of Children against Sexual Exploitation and Sexual Abuse of the year 2007.

The General Assembly for the International Criminal Police Organization- INTERPOL has adopted the Act no. (AG-2009-RES-05).

Arab Convention on Combating Technology Offences.

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